

Application of a Multiscale Temperature Treatment to Multiphysics Calculations in a TRISO Fueled Microreactor

Kevin C. Sawatzky^{1,2,*}, April J. Novak¹, Yinbin Miao²

¹University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, 104 South Wright Street, Illinois, USA;

²Argonne National Laboratory, 9700 South Cass Avenue, Lemont, Illinois, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803564

ABSTRACT

TRistructural ISOtropic (TRISO) fuels are being pursued for several different fission reactor technologies as they have excellent safety and heat transport characteristics. Modeling TRISO fuels presents a severe challenge in multiphysics analysis due to the different length scales heat conduction and neutronics must be resolved on, ranging from μm to m . This work extends Heat Source Decomposition (HSD) to enable the use of nonlinear material properties and heat sources computed by a coarse-mesh neutronics solver, with the goal of resolving deficiencies of fully homogeneous modeling approaches. The technique developed in this work is compared against several homogeneous approaches and a fully explicit heterogeneous model based on a unit cell from the Virtual Test Bed Gas Cooled Microreactor (GCMR). The homogeneous models perform quite well compared to HSD and explicit steady-state multiphysics models of the unit cell when the packing fraction is large (40% for the GCMR) and power density is low. Results for a single-physics nonlinear ramp transient indicate that HSD may be valuable when considering severe reactivity transients where power peaks in a short period of time. This is corroborated by initial experiments applying HSD to a reactivity insertion transient in the whole-core GCMR model.

Keywords: TRISO, Heat Source Decomposition, Multiscale, Multiphysics, Griffin

1. INTRODUCTION

Several reactor vendors are pursuing the use of TRistructural ISOtropic (TRISO) fuels due to the many advantages of the fuel form, including superior fission product retention and excellent heat transport characteristics. This fuel form consists of many individual sub-millimeter concentrically layered particles embedded in a graphite matrix, where the number of particles per fuel element (compact or pebble) is determined by the desired TRISO packing fraction. A prototypical gas-cooled microreactor using a 160 cm tall, 0.85 cm radius fuel compact with a 40% packing fraction would contain approximately 480000 TRISO particles per compact [1]. Meshing and simulating fuel at this level of detail is compute and memory prohibitive, and becomes completely infeasible at whole-core scales with hundreds of compacts. This is known as the *double-heterogeneity* problem in reactor physics, where neutronics and heat conduction must be resolved at the $\mu m - mm$ scales [2] which are several orders of magnitude smaller than the engineering length scales ($cm - m$) of the reactor.

Due to the computational expense of explicitly simulating TRISO fuels, multiphysics simulations often employ homogenization techniques which "smear" the fuel particles and background material together into a set of effective thermal properties and an average heat source for heat conduction simulations [2]. While effective in mitigating the performance penalty inherent to explicit simulations, homogenization techniques are only capable of capturing the long wavelength behavior of the temperature field in fuel compacts [2, 3]. These methods miss the short wavelength behavior caused by localized heat deposition in the fuel kernel during transients, localized kernel temperature peaking caused by the reduced

*kevincs2@illinois.edu

thermal conductivity of the buffer region, and temperature increases caused by particle clustering effects. Previous work performing explicit multiphysics simulations of TRISO compact unit cells has shown that these effects have a substantial impact on integral quantities such as k_{eff} and peak fuel temperature at low packing fractions and/or high power densities [4]. Much of the prior body of work also uses constant thermal properties for TRISO particles, which neglects the impact of temperature variation of said properties which may be non-negligible in the case of heat capacity. To address the shortcomings of previous homogenization methods this work investigates and extends Heat Source Decomposition (HSD) [2,3] to multiphysics models containing nonlinear material properties and heat sources computed by neutronics. The Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) framework [5] is used to implement this modified form of HSD and couple the treatment with the reactor physics code Griffin [6] to investigate its performance for nonlinear multiphysics calculations and the necessity of more advanced temperature treatments.

The remainder of the work is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces HSD and the homogenization strategies evaluated in this work. Section 3 discusses the computational implementation of the explicit, homogeneous, and HSD models. Section 4 compares the approaches presented in this work against the fully explicit TRISO calculations. Section 5 provides some concluding remarks and areas for future work.

2. MULTISCALE HEAT CONDUCTION CALCULATIONS

For TRISO fueled reactors, heat transport through a fuel compact or pebble towards the coolant boundary is governed by the transient heat conduction equation:

$$\rho C_p(\vec{r}, T(\vec{r}, t)) \frac{\partial T(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(k(\vec{r}, T(\vec{r}, t)) \vec{\nabla} T(\vec{r}, t) \right) + \dot{q}(\vec{r}, t), \quad (1)$$

where \vec{r} is the independent spatial variable, t is the independent time variable, $\rho C_p(\vec{r}, T(\vec{r}, t))$ is the heat capacity of the material, $k(\vec{r}, T(\vec{r}, t))$ is the thermal conductivity of the material, $\dot{q}(\vec{r}, t)$ is the volumetric heat production rate and $T(\vec{r}, t)$ is the temperature of the medium. The presence of rapid variations across different length scales for the heat source and thermal properties makes Eq. 1 computationally intractable to solve for whole-core multiphysics reactor analysis. The remainder of this section is dedicated to describing the multiscale method chosen to address the difference in length scales and homogenization strategies used in reactor analysis.

2.1. Heat Source Decomposition

HSD is a multiscale method which decomposes the heat conduction equation over the entire domain into a sum of two components, the macroscale average temperature $T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)$ and a microscale fluctuating temperature $T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t)$. This is accomplished by splitting the heat source into a mean and a fluctuation:

$$\dot{q}(\vec{r}, t) = \langle \dot{q} \rangle(\vec{r}, t) + \tilde{q}(\vec{r}, t), \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \dot{q} \rangle(\vec{r}, t)$ is the mean heat source and $\tilde{q}(\vec{r}, t)$ is the fluctuating heat source [3]. Identically, the mean of $\tilde{q}(\vec{r}, t)$ is zero. Substituting Eq. 2 into Eq. 1 yields:

$$\rho C_p(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t) + T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t)) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t) + T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t) \right] = \nabla \cdot \left(k(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t) + T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t)) \vec{\nabla} \left[T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t) + T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t) \right] \right) + \langle \dot{q} \rangle(\vec{r}, t) + \tilde{q}(\vec{r}, t). \quad (3)$$

When ρC_p and k are independent of temperature the principle of linear superposition can be used to split Eq. 3 into two separate temperature equations for T_{macro} and T_{micro} . In this work, to enable the use

of nonlinear material properties the following approximation is made:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho C_p(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t) + T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t)) &\approx \rho C_p(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) \\ k(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t) + T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t)) &\approx k(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)).\end{aligned}$$

In addition to the need to treat the nonlinearities, the use of the same thermal property functions across both length scales necessitates the resolution of microscale features at the macroscale. Therefore, to avoid the need for a mesh which resolves microscale thermal properties at the macroscale the full thermal conductivity and heat capacity functions are approximated with homogenized equivalents over the particle bed. As Eq. 3 is ultimately discretized with the method of lines in time, a value of T_{macro} from the previous iteration is used to force linearity within a given iteration. Applying these approximations to Eq. 3 allows for the separation of temperature into two equations across two different length scales:

$$\rho C_{p,macro}(T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) \frac{\partial T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_{macro}(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) \vec{\nabla} T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) + \langle \dot{q} \rangle(\vec{r}, t) \quad (4)$$

$$\rho C_p(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) \frac{\partial T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k(\vec{r}, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) \vec{\nabla} T_{micro}(\vec{r}, t)) + \tilde{q}(\vec{r}, t), \quad (5)$$

where $\rho C_{p,macro}$ is the homogenized heat capacity and k_{macro} is the homogenized thermal conductivity. Eq. 5 is solved for a temperature correction over each TRISO particle and added to T_{macro} to correct for the heat source heterogeneity and approximately correct for the heterogeneity in material properties:

$$T(\vec{r}, t) = T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t) + \sum_{j=1}^J T_{micro,j}(\vec{r}, t), \quad (6)$$

where the summation occurs over the j -th TRISO particle. The boundary conditions for Eq. 4 are the same boundary conditions one would apply to the full system. Eq. 5 uses Dirichlet conditions to ensure that the mean temperature fluctuation is zero:

$$T_{micro,j}(\vec{r}, t)|_{\Gamma_j} = -\frac{1}{V_j} \int_{V_j} T_{micro,j}(\vec{r}, t) dV, \quad (7)$$

where V_j and Γ_j are the volume and outer boundary of the j -th particle (respectively) [2,3]. To decrease the computational cost of HSD, Eq. 5 is solved over a 1D r -spherical domain to exploit the symmetry inherent to the heat conduction problem with a Dirichlet boundary condition. To further reduce the computational requirements of the microscale models and avoid difficulties involving projecting solutions between meshes at different length scales, the center temperatures of the TRISO particles are linearly interpolated and used to reconstruct the microscale fluctuating temperature. The accuracy of this approach largely depends on the homogenization strategy used for the thermal properties in Eq. 4; the following section describes the homogenization techniques commonly used in TRISO modeling which are investigated in this work.

2.2. Homogenization Methods

There are many approaches for computing effective thermal conductivities and heat capacities. The simplest approach is to use either a series volume average

$$\chi_{hom} = \sum_{\ell=1}^{N_r} \epsilon_{\ell} \chi_{\ell}, \quad (8)$$

or a parallel volume average

$$\chi_{hom} = \left(\sum_{\ell=1}^{N_r} \frac{\epsilon_{\ell}}{\chi_{\ell}} \right)^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

where χ_{hom} is the homogenized property, N_r is the number of regions, ϵ_ℓ is the phase fraction of region ℓ , and χ_ℓ is the property of region ℓ [3,7]. Physics-informed approaches for homogenization are based on thermal diffusion through a bed of randomly packed spheres, which results in homogenization equations for thermal conductivity based on potential theory. The most commonly used homogenization strategies for thermal conductivity are the Differential Effective Medium Theory (D-EMT) model and the Chiew–Glandt model. This work elects to use the Chiew–Glandt model over the D-EMT model due to the minimal error it introduces [7] and ease of implementation in a MOOSE input file. This homogenization model is given by:

$$k_{hom} = k_m \left(\frac{1 + 2\beta\epsilon_d + (2\beta^3 - 0.1\beta)\epsilon_d^2 + 0.05\epsilon_d^3 \exp(4.5\beta)}{1 - \beta\epsilon_d} \right), \quad (10)$$

where k_{hom} is the homogenized thermal conductivity, k_d is the thermal conductivity of the dispersed phase (TRISO particles), k_m is the thermal conductivity of the matrix material, ϵ_d is the phase fraction of the dispersed phase, k_{hom} is the homogenized thermal conductivity, and β is defined as:

$$\beta = \frac{k_d - k_m}{k_d + 2k_m}. \quad (11)$$

Functional dependence on \vec{r} and T_{macro} are suppressed for brevity. k_d may be computed using Eq. 8 or Eq. 9, however it is more common to use a constant value of thermal conductivity for TRISO particles based on numerical experiments. Heat capacities are nearly exclusively computed with Eq. 8 over the compact and a constant value of the TRISO heat conductivity. The use of a constant heat capacity for the TRISO particle underestimates fuel kernel temperatures during transients. This work determined that a series average at both the compact and particle level is sufficient when the the matrix material is evaluated using point-wise temperatures, and the heat capacity of the particle is evaluated using a nearest neighbor average:

$$\rho C_{p,macro}(T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) = (1 - \epsilon_d)\rho C_{p,m}(\vec{r}, t, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) + \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{\epsilon_d}{V_{j,n}} \left(\int_{V_{j,n}} \rho C_{p,d}(\vec{r}, t, T_{macro}(\vec{r}, t)) dV \right), \quad (12)$$

where $V_{j,n}$ is the subset of the spatial domain classified as closest to TRISO pseudo-particle j . The heat capacity of the dispersed phase is computed pointwise with Eq. 8.

3. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the performance of HSD for practical multiphysics and transient calculations, this work develops an explicit model of a unit cell from the Virtual Test Bed (VTB) Gas Cooled Microreactor (GCMR) [1]. The explicit model contains 2774 TRISO particles in a 0.85 cm radius fuel compact of height 1 cm. TRISO particles are separated from the matrix and exchange heat fluxes and surface temperatures at the boundaries to reduce meshing requirements between the different length scales [4]. Even after segregating the different length scales, the explicit calculation required 9468012 tetrahedral elements across both meshes. The nonlinear property correlations used in this work are identical to the properties used by the fuel performance code BISON for explicit TRISO modeling [8]. Convective boundary conditions are applied on the three coolant channels of the unit cell ($T_{fluid} = 1003.4$ K, $h = 2000$ W m⁻² K⁻¹) while the remaining boundaries use symmetry conditions. Neutronics is solved with the discrete ordinates (S_N) method in Griffin [6] with the same discretization parameters as the GCMR assembly model. Power densities are normalized to a representative value for the GCMR, which is 24 W for a compact of this volume. The coupling scheme for the explicit model can be found in Figure 1. The MOOSE MultiApp system is extensively used in this work as it allows for the separation of

different length scales and different physics into separate applications which broadcast fields to each other during Picard iterations with in-memory data transfers.

The HSD calculations use a similar coupling scheme to standard multiphysics calculations employing homogenization approaches [4], with some added complexity in the form of another layer in the Picard loop. The modified coupled scheme for HSD can be found in Figure 2, where the macroscale and microscale models communicate through power densities, macroscale temperatures, and kernel maximum temperatures. The use of a 1D solve per particle is still quite computationally demanding; future work scaling HSD to whole core problems should investigate the use of a limited number of representative pseudo-particles which are interpolated to obtain T_{micro} .

Figure 1. Explicit coupling scheme during a single Picard iteration.

Figure 2. HSD coupling scheme during a single Picard iteration.

As there are no representative problems that can be easily used to test the transient multiphysics response of the GCMR unit cell explicitly modeled, a single physics power ramp with nonlinear material properties is used to compare different models. Neutronics coupling is removed, and the problem is initialized with steady-state initial conditions with a uniform power density. The total compact power is ramped from 24 W to 240 W over 9 s, and the maximum kernel temperature is compared between each approach over the course of the transient.

4. RESULTS

This section compares two different homogeneous approaches and the HSD method developed in this work against the explicit multiphysics unit cell. The homogeneous calculations are differentiated by the model used to compute k_d , which is either Eq. 8 or Eq. 9. HSD calculations use Eq. 9 as it yielded the best results over Eq. 8. The temperature profile, kernel temperatures transferred to neutronics, and

kernel power densities for the explicit case can be found in Figure 3. The macroscale temperatures, fluctuating temperatures, and kernel temperatures transferred to neutronics for the HSD case can be found in Figure 4. A comparison of the spatial distribution of the homogeneous results is omitted as they are functionally identical to the spatial distribution of the macroscale temperature in Figure 4.

Table I compares the different approaches using various integral approaches to determine the impact of homogenization and if the application of HSD yields any benefit. Some small improvements can be made in integral parameters when using nonlinear HSD; the pure homogeneous approaches perform quite well at the high packing fraction (40%) and low power density considered in this work. However, this is unlikely to be the case for non-microreactor applications as the magnitude of the required temperature correction scales with the power density of the TRISO particles.

Figure 3. Multiphysics results when using an explicit simulation.

Figure 4. Multiphysics results when using HSD.

Table I. Summary of multiphysics results between different approaches

Parameter	Homogeneous (k_d from Eq. 8)	Homogeneous (k_d from Eq. 9)	HSD	Explicit
k_{eff}	1.24697	1.24685	1.24645	1.24611
$\max(T_{kernel})$ (K)	1089	1092	1094	1098
Δk_{eff} (pcm)	-86	-74	-34	—
$\Delta \max(T_{kernel})$ (K)	9	6	4	—

Qualitatively, the effects of particle clustering can be seen in Figure 3 where the kernel temperature exhibits a slight north-west tilt due to the stochastic nature of particle packing. In principle, HSD can accommodate this effect, but the use of linear interpolation in this work to avoid mesh to mesh data transfers between length scales loses this information as nearby particles cannot constructively interfere. In the mean, the compact temperature distribution and the macroscale temperature distribution are also quite similar. The effects of localized power peaking cannot be captured by the approach taken in this work due to the use of linear interpolation of kernel maximum temperatures.

The minimal differences between HSD and homogeneous models for steady-state problems motivate comparisons for transient simulations with nonlinear material properties. Figure 5 compares the single-physics transient response of different homogenization schemes with and without HSD. Series averages for k_d result in large deviations from the explicit model, while the addition of HSD without a specialized treatment of specific heat results in over-predictions of the maximum predicted kernel temperature. Use of Eq. 12 reduces the error on the maximum kernel temperature when using HSD to less than 2 K over the course of the entire transient when Eq. 9 is used for k_d . Overall, HSD with nonlinear material properties and re-evaluated homogenization schemes for the macroscale model proves to be effective at reducing errors in kernel center temperatures when compared to fully homogeneous approaches.

Figure 5. Comparison of various homogenization approaches with or without HSD for the transient test case. Difference is taken with respect to the maximum kernel temperature.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work derives a form of HSD which is capable of treating nonlinear material properties and heat sources. The modified form of HSD is compared against fully homogeneous and explicit heterogeneous calculations using a unit cell from the VTB GCMR model. It was found that this multiscale approach was effective in reducing errors in integral metrics compared to fully homogeneous calculations in steady-state simulations. Biases on the maximum fuel temperature and k_{eff} are minimal for fully homogeneous models with appropriate choices of homogenization schemes for thermal properties; the use of HSD for these problems is likely not necessary for steady-state high packing fraction / low power density applications (such as the GCMR). Larger TRISO fueled reactors have power densities five to ten times larger than that of the GCMR; these multiphysics models will benefit substantially from the use of HSD. Comparisons of HSD and homogeneous approaches to explicit models for a nonlinear ramp transient show significant differences based on the homogenization scheme used. It was found that a combination of parallel averaging for the TRISO particle thermal conductivity and a nearest point average for particle specific heat yielded results comparable to the explicit model when using HSD. Future work should include mesh free mapping techniques to preserve the spatial character of the microscale solution, the use of pseudo-particles to avoid the need for a 1D r-spherical solve at ev-

ery TRISO position, and scaling the approach to whole-core calculations. Figure 6 showcases an initial application of HSD to a point-kinetics driven reactivity insertion transient in the whole-core GCMR model, where HSD is able to account for the deposition of energy in the fuel kernel and the immediate drop in reactivity caused by this highly localized fuel temperature reactivity feedback.

Figure 6. Preliminary application of HSD to a 50 cent reactivity insertion in the whole-core GCMR model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was sponsored by the Multiphysics Applications Technical Area of the U.S. DOE Nuclear Energy Advanced Modeling and Simulation (NEAMS) program. Argonne's efforts were sponsored by the U.S. Department of Energy under Contract DE-AC02-06CH11357. We gratefully acknowledge the computing resources provided on Improv, a high-performance computing cluster operated by the Laboratory Computing Resource Center (LCRC) at Argonne National Laboratory (ANL).

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Stauff *et al.* "Assessment and Validation of NEAMS Tools for High-Fidelity Multiphysics Transient Modeling of Microreactors." Technical Report ANL/NEAMS-24/3, Argonne National Laboratory (2024).
- [2] A. Novak *et al.* "Multiscale Thermal-Hydraulic Modeling of the Pebble Bed Fluoride-Salt-Cooled High-Temperature Reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 154**, p. 107968 (2021).
- [3] R. Stainsby *et al.* "Investigation of Local Heat Transfer Phenomena in a Pebble Bed HTGR Core." Technical Report NR001/RP/002 R01, AMEC (2009).
- [4] A. Hegazy, A. J. Novak, and Rizwan-uddin. "Multiphysics Simulation of TRISO Fuel Compacts and the Effects of Homogenization." In *Proceedings of PHYSOR-2024*. American Nuclear Society, San Fransisco, California, USA (2024).
- [5] G. Giudicelli *et al.* "3.0 - MOOSE: Enabling Massively Parallel Multiphysics Simulations." *SoftwareX*, **volume 26** (2024).
- [6] Y. Wang *et al.* "Griffin: A MOOSE-Based Reactor Physics Application for Multiphysics Simulation of Advanced Nuclear Reactors." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 211**, p. 110917 (2025).
- [7] A. Toptan *et al.* "FEA-Aided Investigation of the Effective Thermal Conductivity in a Medium with Embedded Spheres." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 381**, p. 111355 (2021).
- [8] J. D. Hales, W. Jiang, A. Toptan, and K. Gamble. "BISON TRISO Modeling Advancements and Validation to AGR-1 Data." Technical Report INL/EXT-20-59368, Idaho National Laboratory (2020).